

COTTON RECEIVING RULES IN COTTON MILLS AND COTTON RECEIVING PLACES

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ABSTRACT

In this article, the rules for receiving cotton in cotton mills and cotton receiving facilities, according to the contracting agreement, it will be handed over to the cotton preparation center belonging to the State Cotton Ginnery. A general plan of a sample cotton preparation station is shown. In the point laboratory, vacuum electric moisture meters, devices for determining the contamination of seed cotton, laboratory gins, polarizing microscopes, I and II class technical scales should be modern.

According to the contracting agreement, the cotton crop planted by the clusters is handed over to the cotton processing center of the State Cotton Ginnery. Cotton preparation points are divided into on-site or off-site points depending on their location in relation to the factory. The preparation points at the factory are located in the general territory of the factory, and the farms located about 15 km from this place (from the main factory), and points outside the factory receive cotton from farms located more than 15 km away. Medium-sized cotton processing centers receive up to 10,000 tons of cotton per season. It would not be economically feasible to set up small processing centers that usually receive less than 6,000 tons of cotton, because such centers cannot cover their costs by themselves. The following tasks are assigned to the cotton ginning plant and preparation station to ensure timely receipt of cotton, proper collection, centralized drying and cleaning, and proper storage:

1. To conclude contractual agreements with farms for the sale of cotton and control their implementation;
2. Organization and provision of high-quality cotton picking by machine and by hand on farms and providing guidance on its proper sorting into varieties;
3. Providing farms with current republican standards, price lists of cotton purchase prices and other normative documents;
4. Hanging the main rules of the republican standards, the purchase prices of cotton, and warning notes on fire prevention techniques in a visible place;

The management of the processing centers must familiarize the farm employees with the republican standards, standard samples and the payment procedure for cotton based on the current legislation. For this purpose, at least 10 days before the beginning of harvesting, a council (seminar) should be held on farms with the participation of farmers, mechanizers and suppliers on quality cotton picking and its delivery to the preparation point.

A general plan of a model cotton processing plant is shown, which provides for modern requirements for the organization of cotton processing and cotton storage. All machine-picked cotton is dried and cleaned in the drying-cleaning workshop. A closed cotton warehouse for temporary storage of wet cotton and bunting areas for storage of dried cotton will be established.

The office, laboratory and other auxiliary rooms of the cotton preparation center are usually located in one building. drying-cleaning workshop firehouse, liquid fuel storage, transformer substation, cotton receiving post with 25-ton vehicle scale, entrance gate to the area, border walls, machinery parking area, fire depot, coal storage area, internal gate, sewage pump, 17,500 m³ of water

capacity pool, kitchen, fire pump, water tower and floodlights are appropriately placed in the territory.

A substation with a special 560 k.Watt transformer was built to supply the preparation point with electricity. The point laboratory should have vacuum electric moisture meters, devices for determining the contamination of seed cotton, laboratory gins, polarizing microscopes, I and II class technical scales and other equipment. In addition, each cotton processing station should be equipped with 12 receiving mechanisms, 12 18-meter conveyors, 10 ladders, bunt breaking and cotton digging machines for every ten thousand tons of cotton.

In order to fulfill the annual state plan for cotton production, cotton ginning factories and their related cotton processing centers must meet the following requirements for receiving cotton brought from the fields on time, for centralized drying and cleaning, and for good storage:

- to conclude a contractual agreement with the cotton growing community, company and other farms for the sale of the whole harvest to the state every year and check its implementation;

- explanation on how to improve the quality of hand-picked and machine-picked cotton on the farm and how to properly sort it;

- strict compliance with the rules and norms established in state standards when receiving cotton;

- ensuring uninterrupted and efficient operation of drying-cleaning workshops;- accurate and timely settlement with cotton suppliers for received cotton;

- separation of received cotton into separate batches according to selection and industrial varieties according to its method and field groups, and seed cotton into separate batches according to reproduction;

- check the quality of the stored cotton in time and load and send it according to the factory plan;

- during cotton storage, drying, cleaning and sending to the factory, its quality should not be damaged and its waste should not be allowed;

- correct accounting of the cotton sent to the factory at the point of preparation and of the cotton stored at the point of preparation by weighing and determining its quality at the factory; taking measures to reduce the costs of receiving, storing, drying and cleaning cotton and delivering it to the factory;

- taking measures in accordance with the rules of fire protection and safety techniques at all stages of cotton preparation, taking measures to fully utilize the mechanisms used during cotton reception, storage and transportation;

- taking measures to save and spend the transport equipment, tarpaulins, bags, laboratory equipment and other economic materials used during cotton preparation;

- the duty of the cotton preparation centers is to temporarily store the seeds brought from the cotton ginning plant and to distribute them to the farms on time in accordance with the rules.

Cotton fiber produced in cotton gins is divided into seven varieties according to the state standard. For this reason, the classifiers that receive seeded cotton separate the part that gives good quality fiber from each type of cotton, depending on its appearance, and collect it in a separate batch:

1st grade cotton - the part that produces excellent grade fiber depending on the size, color, well-opened, and restraint of the pelts;

III grade cotton - the part that gives more IV grade fiber;

IV type cotton - the part that gives more IV and V type fibers;

From the machine-picked cotton, in order to get more type I fiber, its well-ripened part is separated separately.

The territory of the cotton processing plant is divided into two or three zones according to the order of the factory director. In zone 1, located near the entrance gate of the three-zone preparation points, the classifier determines the quality of cotton and takes a sample for the laboratory; In zone 2, cotton is weighed and the big classifier writes the acceptance document; Depending on the batch of cotton received in zone 3, it is placed in open or closed warehouses and re-checked by the classifier.

If cotton is received in a two-zone system, a large classifier checks the quality of cotton and weighs it in zone 1. If the quality of the cotton does not meet the standard requirements, it will not be transferred beyond zone 1 and returned for drying and cleaning.

The laboratory of the cotton processing center creates a passport card for each batch of received cotton. In the passport, the selective and industrial type of cotton, reproduction, field group, warehouse number, the time of the start and end of the batch, its weight and the classifier's surname are indicated.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it can be said that the rules for accepting cotton in cotton factories and cotton reception centers must be approached with important tasks and modern methods. is a type of lesson. It should also be carried out in an integrated, system.

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